

PREPARATION OF SAXAUL SEEDS FOR AERIAL SEEDING AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF AERIAL SEEDING

¹Urakov S.M., ²Turdiev S.A.

¹Philosophy Doctor on Agricultural Sciences, Tashkent State Agrarian University

²Professor, Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Abstract. *In the given article the advantages of processing the wings, peeling and humimax solution of black saxaul seeds are presented with the aim of expanding the areas of natural and cultural saxaul forests in the Aral Bay region. In particular, in the period of many years of scientific research, the results of sowing black saxaul seeds with and without a wing in field and laboratory conditions, according to positive indicators of the research process, a patent for invention N. IAP 06866 was obtained in 2022 and the conclusions were presented.*

Keywords: *island region, green cover, 2006-2021, "Gumimax", shelled seeds, wind, shelling.*

Introduction. According to the physical and geographical position of the world, it includes various geographical landscapes such as glaciers, seas, mountains, swamps, forests, steppes, deserts, sandy deserts. While studying these physical and geographical territories, the targeted use of resources and objects, expansion of forest areas, afforestation based on desert plants such as yulung, black-barak, white and black saxaul, in the development of steppe deserts and sandy desert lands, increasing the ecological level of the population in agriculture and ensuring the stability of the bioecological balance are some of the priority areas. In the world, the total area of sandy desert lands is 21.0 million km² (excluding the polar deserts of Antarctica and the Arctic) or about 14% of the land surface, while polar deserts make up more than 20%, the largest desert is considered to be Sakhara, which occupies the entire northern part of the African continent. The area of the sandy site is 162,000 hectares (1,620 km²), located 30 km east of the city of Kherson, Ukraine.

Many scientific studies are being conducted around the world on the development of desert areas and mitigation of the ecological balance. Scientific research on the development of methods for mechanical protection of sands, planting of herbaceous plants, creation of green covers of trees and shrubs are considered relevant. In the countries of North Africa with large areas of sandy deserts, Arabia and China, scientific research is being conducted on the development of effective and resource-saving technologies for growing from seeds to create saxaul forests, increase the fertility of saxaul seeds, increase the yield, level of seedlings and their storage.

In our republic, this sandy desert occupies an area of about 9.7 million hectares. One of the types of desert plants used as landscaping in the territories of these desert regions is saxaul. Scientific research is still being conducted on the propagation of saxaul by seeds without cultivation and the creation of forests by planting seedlings, and certain results have been achieved. However, the technology for removing the wings, peeling and flying out of saxaul seeds has not been developed. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in our republic defines the tasks of "creating an additional 500 thousand hectares of green space on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea and increasing their total area to 2.5 million hectares or 78% of the country's territory by the end of 2026". In this regard, it is important to conduct scientific research on the collection, sorting, refinement, peeling and planting of saxaul seeds that are highly resistant to

adverse environmental factors in the Aral region, lands with a complex melioration state and their introduction into production. In this regard, the goal was set to develop a method for preparing seeds for planting by removing the wings and peeling the seeds of black saxaul, as well as preparing high-quality seeds for planting using a hang glider in order to create greenery in the Aral Bay area and the dry bottom of the Aral Sea.

For achieving the set goal, it was necessary to complete the following tasks, including: determination of the biomorphological parameters of saxaul seeds and analysis of the initial parameters of seed germination processes using different sowing methods, development of a method for pre-processing (sorting and drying) saxaul seeds; trimming and sorting saxaul seeds using a special device (C 17512537-002:2022); development of a technology for shelling winged saxaul seeds, development of a method for sowing shelled seeds in the sandy deserts of the Arolbay region using a hang glider.

These tasks were carried out based on the following methods: Conducting field and industrial experiments, Recommendation for "Accelerating the formation of vegetation by supporting natural forest regeneration from seeds on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea" (2014), Recommendation for "Creation of forest ecosystems on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea" (2014), Germination of tree and shrub seeds in laboratory conditions according to the requirements of SOST 13.056.6-75, SOST 13855-87 "Fruits of sand-restoring tree species, technical conditions "Methodological recommendations for phytomeliorative reconstruction of degraded and desertified pastures of the Russian Federation using innovative environmental resource-saving technologies" (Federal Scientific Center of Agroecology, Russian Academy of Sciences) by the method of winging saxaul seeds with special device (C 17512537 -002:2022), field statistical analysis of the results obtained during experiments using the Microsoft Excel computer program calculated using B.A. Dospekhov's method.

Research results and discussion.

The saxaul plant is one of the main tree species used in the improvement of sandy desert lands, in the creation of protective forest groves and the creation of green covers.

Of current importance is the germination and improvement of the quality of cultivated forest plantations created in desert areas. Accordingly, in the conditions of the Aral Sea region, when expanding the area of natural and cultivated saxaul forests, high efficiency was achieved by planting black saxaul based on dewinged, sorted and cleaned seeds.

During our long-term scientific research from 2006 to 2021, a method for separating the wings of black saxaul seeds and cleaning them before planting was tested, based on the research results, a patent for an invention was obtained in 2022. It is known that due to small wings, saxaul seeds face some difficulties when planting in sandy desert areas. Seeds with such special wings are characterized by low spreadability.

In the device for removing the wings of seeds of desert plants, the seeds were deprived of wings, and quality seeds were sorted by partial wind. The resulting seeds: taking into account the time of planting, the weather conditions of the region, they were placed in a working solution, while the seeds were sorted again, against root rot and other diseases and sprayed with the substance "Gumimax" with a concentration of 0.01%, and all parts were mixed and processed. In addition, a method of peeling was developed by processing the dewinged and sorted seeds with clean ravine soil, dried swamp soil, which is crushed type rock soil.

The advantage of this method is that the work is done quickly and without much effort. In addition, the cleaned seeds fall into small holes on the surface of the earth, around dried plants, and are buried by the wind by 0.1-10.0 mm. As early as 1925, scientific work was conducted to prevent landslides and strengthen sand, but deep research on improving germination and seed retention, as well as hulling of saxaul seeds, was not conducted.

During research, there was found out the idea of hulling saxaul seeds after separating them with a special device. Fertility can be increased by forming an outer shell on the seeds by treating them with a straw wall or clean rocky soil and other organic and inorganic fillers to reduce the size of saxaul seeds, evenly distribute the seeds and improve their quality germination. It can also be said that wet soils with high dryness, extracted from large ditches, can also be used.

During the research, a special seed spreading device USM 1 (Ts 17512537-001:2022) and the main working element - the converter of the seed spreading rate (dispenser) SHNEH, a guide hole, a battery and other equipment were installed on the hang glider. Peeling was carried out as follows: soil was crushed in a dry state (90% of the volume) and dried, stimulator 20 g. Per 1 liter of water + mixed water mass. The seeds were sprayed with water using a sprayer. It is necessary to moisten the seeds so that they do not stick to each other. After that they are sprayed with the growth substance "Gumimax" in a concentration of 0.01-0.1% and all parts are mixed. It is recommended to dry them in the open air to increase the degree of spraying. After peeling, the seeds are on average 1.2-1.6 times heavier (compared to the control). In this case, their spraying capacity increases, it becomes convenient to spray with various technical means. Nutrients appear in the shell around the seed. Gumimax consists of peat-humin, it is harmless (liquid). Contains sodium and potassium (4.5 g / l), phosphorus (4.5 g / l), copper, zinc and manganese. In laboratory conditions, it was found that in Petri dishes, peeled seeds germinate up to 80% per day, their length was 3 mm, the length of the roots was 15 mm. On the third day, the length of the control (without shell) was 3 mm, germination was 1%. It was noted that the length of the rhizomes was two times shorter (8 mm). After 17 days, the germination of peeled seeds was 87%, control - 60%. The upper part of unshelled seeds (10%) was covered with fungi, and the shelled ones were healthy and no diseases were observed. The average length of sprouts from seeds with a shell was 5 mm, the length of the rhizomes was 40-65 mm, the average length of the control variant without a shell was 5 mm; the length of the rhizomes was 30-43 mm (observed 17 days after sowing the seeds).

The health of plants sprouted from peeled seeds was noted, which is a consequence of seed treatment.

Its useful qualities were additionally demonstrated by sowing peeled seeds in a sandy desert area of Shafirkon State Forestry Enterprise with an area of 300 hectares using a hang glider. Observations conducted on April 30, 2012 showed that peeled seeds have a higher germination rate.

On average, there were 2500-2700 plants per hectare with a height of 15-20 cm. The control variants had a height of 4-12 cm, the number averaged 1700-1800 plants/ha with an average number of 600-700 pcs. per hectare (in the control variant, this figure was 55-80 pcs./ha).

At the same time, while processing the branches of an 8-10-year-old saxaul in forestry with a preparation used against insects, diseases and pests, as well as a germination agent, gumimax, no fungi were observed on its branches and 10-15% of the control saxaul had fungi. The peeled seeds were sown manually in rows on the sandy plains of the dry bottom of the Aral Sea in the

fields of the former Fisherman's Bay. The length of each row is 200 loops meters, a total is higher than 800. The seeds are planted per meter. As a control, unpeeled seeds were planted in rows.

Figure 1. The first 1-2 years of performance growth of a black saxaul, planted by a glider.

Figure 2. Growth rate of black saxaul over 4-5 years, planted by hang glider

Effect of covering methods on seed germination by plant species: in order to increase the productivity of desert pastures, seeds of valuable forage plants belonging to various life forms were planted and studied.

In 2006-2009, the first work began on planting seeds of desert plants with their hulling and drying on the basis of a mixture of clay, sand, humus, organic and mineral fertilizers. Before planting, seeds were collected from healthy black saxaul trees on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea. Seed germination was tested in room conditions. On March 22, 2009, 400 black saxaul seeds were sown in Petri dishes.

Figure 3. Germination of peeled saxaul seedlings

Release dynamics: On March 24, the number of sprouts was 8, on March 25 - 18, on March 27 - 30, on March 29 - 51, on March 30 - 348 or 87% (Fig. 3).

Field experiments were conducted in 4 options:

Option 1. Black saxaul seeds were planted in soil, which was a sandy layer of the river. Then they were covered with sand 0.5 cm thick (control variant).

Option 2. The shelled mass, consisting of a mixture of soil 50% + humus 50% + urea 20 g / l + water.

Option 3: The collapsed mass, consisting of a mixture of earth 70% + humus 30% + urea 20 g / l + water.

Option 4: crust mass consisting of a mixture of waterlogged dried black (brick or straw) soil 90% + humus 10% + stimulator 20 g / l + water removed from the ditch. Dehorned seeds were placed in the working solution for 30 minutes, dead seeds that were on the water were removed (the seeds were sorted), those with reduced inhibitory properties, and the sorted seeds and other components were thoroughly mixed (before adding water) and again thoroughly mixed after adding water. The diameter of the holes of the meat grinder is 7 mm.

Figure 4. Saxaul seed germination rates

In the first option, on March 22, 200 meters of sand were planted in the field. Saxaul seeds without a shell (254,600 pcs.) were covered with 0.5 cm of sand. As of March 30, the seed germination rate was 15% (38,190 pcs.). At the end of the growing season, on September 15, the seedling survival rate was on average 1% (2,500 pcs.).

In the second option, on March 22, 200 meters of sand were planted in the field. Cleaned (50% soil + 50% humus + 20 g/l urea + water) Saxaul seeds (254.6 thousand pcs.) were planted. As of March 30, the seed germination rate was 28% (71,288 pcs.). At the end of the growing season, i.e. September 15, the seedling survival rate was on average 1% (2560 pcs.).

In the third option, on March 22, 200 meters of sand. The field was planted with cleaned (70% soil + 30% humus + 20 g/l urea + water) saxaul seeds (254.6 thousand pcs.). As of March 30, the seed germination rate was 20% (50920 pcs.). At the end of the growing season, i.e. September 15, the average seedling survival rate was 2% (5092 pcs.).

In the fourth option, on March 22, 200 meters of sand. Saxaul seeds (254,600 pcs.) were sown in the field of purified soil (extracted from the soil, waterlogged dry black (brick or straw) soils 90% + humus 10% + stimulant 20 g / l + water). As of March 30, the seed germination was 47% (119,662 pcs.). At the end of the growing season, i.e. September 15, the average survival rate of seedlings was 4.5% (11,457 pcs.).

In March 2010, granulated black saxaul seeds were sown every 10 m in rows 40-50 cm wide. A total of 200 plants were planted, leaving a width of 40-50 cm. 1 running metre: 9-12 pieces, black saxaul 7-12 cm high, sprouted.

In the control variant, black saxaul seeds were sown to a depth of 1-2 cm without a shell, 1 metre: 20-25 sprouts (width of a metre 40-50 cm), height 6-17 cm.

The third variant was an experiment on planting black saxaul seeds without shelling and without burying them in the soil. In this case, the number of black saxaul seedlings per 1 m/m with a width of 40-50 cm was 5-10 and the height of the seedlings was 6-18 cm. From this it can be concluded that sowing saxaul seeds without covering with soil gives a certain positive result for the growth of desert plants with sufficient precipitation in winter and spring. In the experimental orders, although the initial germination of seedlings in the shell-less variant was high, their survival rate by autumn was low. Despite the fact that the initial germination of seedlings in the shelled variants is low, their survival rate in autumn is high.

Increasing the productivity of the barking black saxaul in small plots:

On December 7, 2012, the black saxaul seeds were sown using a hang glider in Shafirkon forestry. The seeds were separated from the fins by rubbing them against a metal mesh, and then the seeds with the fin removed were spread on the ground. They were sprayed with an aqueous solution of the growth agent, then sprinkled with sifted fine rotted manure, soil and sprayed with a small amount of an aqueous solution of an anesthetic agent using small sprayers.

The seeds and other ingredients were mixed well by hand with a shovel and covered with plastic wrap. The following day, the seeds were taken to the plot and sown in the designated place.

These peeled seeds were brought little by little and planted in an open field (in two barrels) in Tashkent conditions. No growth was observed in winter. In early April 2013, the seeds began to germinate. Their height was measured on April 13, 16, and 21. Information on their growth is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 shows that peeled saxaul seeds (and those treated with growth agents) were 138.4% taller than the control, 167.0% taller on April 16, and 162.8% taller on April 21.

It should be noted that the seeds were planted in sand brought from the river. Their upper part was not covered with sand. No seedlings were observed in winter.

Table 4

Data on the growth of peeled saxaul seeds

Time of sowing seeds	Measured time	Average height of saxaul,		Difference	
		Peeled (first option)	Controlled (second option)	cm	%
13. XII.2012 й.	13.IB.2013 й.	4,25 cm	3,07 cm	1,18	138,4
13. XII.2012 й.	16.IB.2013 й.	6,36 cm	3,81 cm	2,55	167,0
13. XII.2012 й.	21.IB.2013 й.	8,14 cm	5,0 cm	3,14	162,8

The number of bruised saxaul plants per 1 m² of area was as follows (as of April 21).

In the first variant 448 units/m².

In the second variant 338 units/m².

Observational work was continued to study plant growth.

While black saxaul seeds were coated and placed in Petri dishes and treated with the growth stimulator "Gummimax - double strength" (seeds without wings), the number of germinating seeds after 24 hours was 96% compared to the seeds of the control variant (untreated seeds, without growth stimulator, without a shell, without wings) began to germinate from the day and remained for 10 days.

After 24 hours, the pelleted, wingless and Gummimax Double Strength treated sprout seeds had an average height of the above-ground part of 5 mm and a root length of 53.6 mm, which is 10.72 times longer than the above-ground part, after 24 hours. The height of the above-ground part of the saxaul seeds was 5 mm, the root length was 38.3 mm.

The practical results of the studies are as follows:

For the first time in our republic, in the conditions of sandy desert lands of 4 districts, saxaul seeds were wingless and cleaned, and the efficiency of sorted cleaned seeds was studied;

a resource-saving technology for air sowing of saxaul seeds in desert areas using a motorized hang glider (aviation) was developed, a certificate was received from the State Unitary Enterprise "Consultative Center for Intellectual Property" and entered into the Register under number N. 004526;

a method for hulling saxaul seeds was developed and patent for invention N. IAP 06866 was received by the Intellectual Property Agency under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Due to the method of preparing saxaul seeds for air seeding, the peeled seeds made it possible to lay green covers on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea and on 17,480 hectares in the Aral Bay area.

Conclusion. The following is a list of the most important aspects of agricultural production: The use of agricultural machinery to produce agricultural products requires the use of special equipment, which allows the production of 500-600 kg of grain per hectare to produce 500 hectares of grain per hectare and a total of 250 hectares of grain per hectare. The goal of this study

is to increase the number of students, who have completed their studies and to provide them with additional training. The interest rate of 1% is 2500 USD. The minimum vegetation period is 70 hectares per hectare of land for a minimum of 300 hectares of land. The daily average of 4-5 hours is 100 km. The main ingredient of the hang glider is 20% hydroxyapatite granules and 20% hydroxyapatite granules (such as jellyfish and others) with a diameter of 2.5 mm and a thick layer of hydroxyapatite (combination of hydroxyapatite) with a spherical shape.

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